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“Педагогик ва психологик тадқиқотлар” журнали 6 та халқаро маълумотлар базаларида индексланган бўлиб, жорий йил учун UIF 2023 = 8.2 “импакт-фактор” кўрсаткичига эга. Ўзбекистон Республикаси Олий таълим, фан ва инновациялар вазирлиги ҳузуридаги Олий аттестация комиссиясининг 2023 йил 24 июлдаги 01-02/1199-сонли хатига мувофиқ ушбу журналда чоп этилган мақолалар хорижий мақолалар сифатида тан олинади.

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EFFECTIVE METHODS OF TEACHING READING TO YOUNG ADULTS

ANNOTATION

This article investigates optimal strategies for teaching reading to young adults, focusing on pedagogical approaches that align with their unique cognitive and emotional development. Emphasizing the integration of technology, the research explores how digital tools can enhance engagement and comprehension. Furthermore, the article advocates for a dynamic instructional environment that considers individual learning preferences, fosters critical thinking skills, and nurtures a positive attitude towards reading. By examining the synergy of theoretical foundations and practical methodologies, this research aims to offer insights into effective teaching practices tailored to the specific needs of young adult learners.

Keywords: pedagogical approaches, unique cognitive, emotional development, integration of technology, dynamic instructional environment, critical thinking skills, synergy of theoretical foundations.

ЭФФЕКТИВНЫЕ МЕТОДЫ ОБУЧЕНИЯ ЧТЕНИЮ МОЛОДЕЖИ

АННОТАЦИЯ

В этой статье исследуются оптимальные стратегии обучения чтению молодых людей, уделяя особое внимание педагогическим подходам, которые соответствуют их уникальному когнитивному и эмоциональному развитию. Подчеркивая интеграцию технологий, исследование исследует, как цифровые инструменты могут улучшить взаимодействие и понимание. Кроме того, статья выступает за создание динамичной учебной среды, которая учитывает индивидуальные предпочтения в обучении, развивает навыки критического мышления и воспитывает позитивное отношение к чтению. Изучая синергию теоретических основ и практических методологий, это исследование направлено на то, чтобы предложить эффективные методы преподавания, адаптированные к конкретным потребностям молодых взрослых учащихся.

Ключевые слова: педагогические подходы, уникальное познавательное, эмоциональное развитие, интеграция технологий, динамичная учебная среда, навыки критического мышления, синергия теоретических основ.

YOSHLARNI SAMARALI O'QITISH USULLARI

ANNOTATSIYA

Ushbu maqolada yoshlarga o'qishni o'rgatishning optimal strategiyalari ko'rib chiqiladi, ularning o'ziga xos kognitiv va hissiy rivojlanishiga mos keladigan pedagogik yondashuvlarga e'tibor qaratiladi. Texnologiya integratsiyasini ta'kidlagan holda, tadqiqot raqamli vositalar o'zaro ta'sir va tushunishni qanday yaxshilashi mumkinligini o'rganadi. Bundan tashqari, maqola individual ta'lim afzalliklarini hisobga olgan holda, tanqidiy fikrlash qobiliyatlarini rivojlantiradigan va o'qishga ijobiy munosabatni rivojlantiradigan dinamik o'quv muhitini yaratishni targ'ib qiladi. Nazariy asoslar va amaliy metodologiyalarning sinergiyasini o'rganish orqali ushbu tadqiqot yosh o'quvchilarning o'ziga xos ehtiyojlariga moslashtirilgan samarali o'qitish usullarini taklif qilishga qaratilgan.

Kalit so'zlar: pedagogik yondashuvlar, noyob kognitiv, hissiy rivojlanish, texnologiya integratsiyasi, dinamik o'quv muhiti, tanqidiy fikrlash qobiliyatlari, nazariy asoslarning sinergiyasi.

Introduction

In the realm of reading education, the integration of real-world applications serves as a bridge between classroom learning and the practicalities of everyday life. By connecting reading materials to tangible, real-world scenarios, educators empower students to see the relevance and application of their literacy skills, fostering a deeper understanding and appreciation for the power of reading beyond academic settings. Connect reading to real-life situations and applications. Explore case studies, articles, and news relevant to their lives, encouraging them to see reading as a tool for understanding and navigating the world around them. Real-world applications provide a context for the knowledge gained through reading. Students are better equipped to understand and retain information when they can see how it relates to their own lives, experiences, and the world around them [1, 2].

Reading skills are fundamental in nearly every profession. By incorporating real-world texts, such as industry reports, manuals, and workplace communications, educators prepare students for the literacy demands they will encounter in their future careers, enhancing overall career readiness. Integrating current news articles and events into reading materials exposes students to real-world issues. This not only broadens their perspectives but also equips them with the critical reading skills needed to navigate and analyze information in an era of constant information flow. Real-world applications extend to financial literacy, an essential life skill. Reading materials related to budgeting, financial reports, and investment guides provide students with the literacy tools necessary for making informed financial decisions as they navigate adulthood [3].

Reading about civic issues, government policies, and historical events empowers students to become informed and engaged citizens. By connecting literature to civic responsibilities, educators foster a sense of social responsibility and encourage active participation in the democratic process. Real-world scenarios often require problem-solving and critical thinking skills. Incorporating texts that present challenges, case studies, or dilemmas allows students to apply their reading skills to analyze situations, make informed decisions, and develop solutions. Real-world applications facilitate cross-curricular connections, demonstrating how literacy is an integral part of various subjects. From reading scientific articles to interpreting historical documents, students understand that reading is a versatile skill applicable across diverse academic domains. Reading materials that highlight community issues and initiatives bring education closer to students' immediate surroundings. This connection to the local community fosters a sense of responsibility, encouraging students to explore how their literacy skills can contribute to positive change.

In the bustling world of education, the concept of Sustained Silent Reading (SSR) has emerged as a powerful and contemplative practice. This dedicated time for uninterrupted personal reading not only fosters a love for literature but also provides a myriad of cognitive, emotional, and educational benefits for readers of all ages. Dedicate specific time for sustained silent reading, allowing young adults to choose books they are passionate about. This self-directed approach not only builds autonomy but also nurtures a love for reading. The power of silence is unleashing potential through sustained silent reading which we discuss such stages as Creating a Reading Culture, Fostering Independence, Building Reading Stamina, Enhancing Comprehension Skills, Exploring Diverse Genres, Promoting Stress Reduction, Encouraging Reflection and Connection and Facilitating Teacher-Student Bond.

- Creating a Reading Culture: sustained silent reading contributes to the creation of a reading culture within educational settings. By designating specific time for personal reading, schools cultivate an environment where literature is valued, and students understand the importance of incorporating reading into their daily lives [4, 5].

- Fostering Independence: SSR promotes independent reading habits. During this time, students have the autonomy to choose books based on their interests and preferences, fostering a sense of ownership over their reading experiences and nurturing a lifelong habit of reading for pleasure.

- Building Reading Stamina: The sustained nature of SSR sessions builds reading stamina over time. As students engage in uninterrupted reading, they gradually develop the ability to focus for extended periods, enhancing their overall reading endurance and concentration skills.

- Enhancing Comprehension Skills: The quiet and focused environment of SSR allows students to immerse themselves in the reading material, leading to enhanced comprehension. Uninterrupted reading sessions enable deeper engagement with the text, promoting a more profound understanding of the content.

- Exploring Diverse Genres: SSR encourages students to explore diverse genres and authors. With the freedom to choose their reading material, students may venture into genres they might not have considered before, broadening their literary horizons and fostering a love for diverse forms of literature.

- Promoting Stress Reduction: In the midst of academic demands, SSR serves as a moment of tranquility. The quiet, uninterrupted reading time provides a welcome break from the hustle and bustle of the classroom, promoting stress reduction and contributing to overall well-being.

- Encouraging Reflection: SSR creates space for reflection and personal connection with the text. Students can immerse themselves in the narrative, relate to characters, and contemplate the themes presented in the books, fostering a deeper emotional and intellectual connection with literature.

- Facilitating Teacher-Student Bond: The shared experience of Sustained Silent Reading can facilitate a unique bond between teachers and students. Teachers, too, participate in SSR, setting an example as avid readers. This shared activity fosters a sense of community and a shared appreciation for the value of reading.

Literacy workshops stand as beacons of interactive and engaging learning experiences within the realm of education. These workshops, designed to enhance reading skills and foster a deeper appreciation for language, offer a dynamic platform for students to explore literature, develop critical thinking, and cultivate a love for reading that extends beyond the classroom. Organize workshops focusing on specific aspects of literacy, such as critical analysis, creative writing, or vocabulary building. These targeted sessions provide concentrated skill development and foster a deeper appreciation for language. Literacy workshops are characterized by their dynamic and interactive nature. Unlike traditional classroom settings, workshops provide a lively space where students actively engage with reading materials, participate in discussions, and collaborate on various literacy-focused activities.

One of the primary objectives of literacy workshops is to target specific literacy skills. Whether focusing on critical analysis, vocabulary expansion, or creative writing, these workshops allow educators to tailor activities to meet the specific needs and developmental levels of the participants. Literacy workshops foster a sense of community and collaboration. Participants often work together on projects, engage in group discussions, and share insights, creating an environment that emphasizes the social aspect of learning and encourages the exchange of ideas.

Workshops provide the flexibility to explore a wide range of literary genres and styles. From classic literature to contemporary works, participants have the opportunity to delve into diverse literary landscapes, broadening their understanding and appreciation for different forms of expression. Literacy workshops serve as incubators for critical thinking skills. Through activities such as literary analysis, interpretation, and reflection, participants are challenged to think deeply about the texts they encounter, fostering analytical skills that extend beyond the workshop setting [6].

The workshop format allows for personalized learning experiences. Participants can choose materials that align with their interests, and educators can tailor activities to address individual strengths and areas for improvement, creating a more responsive and student-centered approach to literacy development. Literacy workshops often bridge the gap between literature and real-world applications. Participants may engage in activities that connect literary themes to contemporary issues, encouraging them to see the relevance of literature in understanding and addressing broader societal concerns. Ultimately, literacy workshops contribute to the cultivation of a lifelong love for reading. By making the learning experience enjoyable, interactive, and personally meaningful, workshops instill a passion for literature that extends beyond academic requirements, nurturing a habit of reading for pleasure.

Conclusion

Real-world applications serve as a cornerstone in the evolution of reading education, transcending the boundaries of traditional classroom learning. By grounding literacy skills in practical, real-life contexts, educators empower students to see the intrinsic value of reading as a tool for understanding, navigating, and shaping the world around them. As students embark on their educational journeys, the integration of real-world applications ensures that reading becomes not just a skill, but a powerful instrument for active engagement and lifelong learning. In the symphony of educational strategies, Sustained Silent Reading emerges as a melody of tranquility and profound learning. By dedicating time to silent, independent reading, educators sow the seeds for a lifelong love of literature while nurturing a range of cognitive and emotional benefits. As the pages turn in the books chosen during SSR, students embark on a journey of personal discovery, imagination, and intellectual growth. In the stillness of Sustained Silent Reading, the power of the written word comes alive, creating a harmonious space where minds flourish and a lifelong love for reading blossoms.

In the symphony of educational methodologies, literacy workshops emerge as a harmonious and impactful crescendo. These workshops, with their emphasis on dynamic learning, targeted skill development, and fostering a genuine love for reading, play a pivotal role in shaping literate, thoughtful, and engaged individuals. As participants embark on the literary journey within the walls of a literacy workshop, they not only enhance their reading skills but also unlock the doors to a world of imagination, critical thinking, and lifelong learning. Teaching reading to young adults requires a multifaceted approach that considers their individual needs and the dynamic landscape of today's educational environment. By incorporating these effective strategies, educators can inspire a lifelong love for reading and empower young adults with essential literacy skills for their future endeavors.

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